

Scaffolding instruction for improvement in learning English language skills

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ABSTRACT

Students who learn English as a foreign language (EFL) or English as a second language (ESL) often struggle with limited vocabulary and poor reading comprehension skills. This action research explores the effectiveness of implementing scaffolding instruction for university level EFL/ESL students in improving their language learning skills, namely critical reading, and study skills for reading. A sample of 36 foundation year students was involved in two cycles of intervention. Triangulation of data collection was done after each cycle through student survey (SS), language learning assessment (LLA) tasks and an observation checklist to measure the impact of the proposed practice on the improvement in the participants' learning. The scaffolding techniques used were soft versus hard (support provided only till needed), chunking (breaking down information), modelling (giving clear examples), bridging (using prior knowledge) and contextualizing (making connections). Both the quantitative and qualitative data revealed that scaffolding instruction significantly improved the participants' language learning skills. For sustainable education, the findings emphasize the importance of conducting scaffolding instruction in small groups, assigning pre-planned and well-structured tasks with clear instructions, and providing scaffolding 'as and when needed' especially in a mixed ability group of EFL/ESL students.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This research study aimed to improve the critical reading skills and the study skills through scaffolding instruction to support the English language learning of university level students. It also emphasized the impact of conducting action research on professional growth through action and reflection. Both the 20th century psychologists, Lewin and Vygotsky, have presented original ideas on human behavior in an ecological and cultural perspective and their theories of action research and activity theory are considered largely as 'methods to improve practice' [1]. These two theories inspired the design of the present investigation to practice scaffolding instruction. The study was conducted on Foundation year students, in a teachers' college in Bahrain, who are required to enroll in an English reading and writing course which encourages them to learn and consistently practice different reading skills. However, students struggle with processing the information, following instructions and recognizing correct sentence structure. Due to these, and the limited vocabulary in English language, their comprehension skills are impeded. Even those who are usually good at oral communication need initial support. The course prepares these teacher candidates, who

are learning English as a foreign language or English as a second language (EFL/ESL), for academic reading and writing tasks that are required in the Bachelor of Education Program (B.Ed.). English, being the medium of instruction for core subjects, necessitates expanding its understanding. The insights gained led to further reflection and a pertinent question: Is it so, for all students who learn English as a second language? A literature review revealed several supporting studies with ESL students in a teacher's college or in higher education [2]–[9].

An empirical study conducted by Asmari [3] investigating the barriers in learning English faced by Saudi preparatory year students reports that the students face difficulties in proper pronunciation, appropriate grammatical structures and necessary vocabulary items which contribute to weak oral proficiency. The students strongly agree that it is an important skill to continue their studies at tertiary level [3]. According to Wachyunni [6], reading skills in EFL context are important for students at a university level because almost all academic activities in this environment require reading skills. Furthermore, online teaching during COVID-19 prompted the need to explore different and more efficient approaches to make learning more useful, tackle losing students' motivation and to achieve the intended learning outcomes of reading and writing courses for ESL students. Arora [10] emphasizes the need for multi-dimensional and sustainable pedagogies based on learning from the experience and insights of COVID-19. Addressing these contextual needs, the literature revealed that a collaborative instructional scaffolding model for ESL students in their preparatory year of higher education, based in sociocultural theory of Lev Vygotsky, is supported by quite a few publications [4]–[6], [11]–[16]. For EFL/ESL/ESP teachers and curriculum designers in particular, the findings of the most recent study by Ibrahim *et al.* [12] show notable benefits of scaffolding instruction and recommend using collaborative strategic reading (CSR) in collaborative learning (CL). The purpose of this action research was to practice scaffolding instruction in improving language learning skills of Foundation year students. It was proposed to scaffold an asynchronous independent reading activity, as and when needed, with guidelines, explanation, and moderation. The instructional support was based in Vygotsky's theory of scaffolding and cognitive learning [17], [18].

Literature on different aspects of the present study was reviewed in multiple directions. First, an in-depth understanding of Vygotsky's theoretical framework led to the adaptation made to it, pedagogical implications, and its link with the stages of action research process based in transformative reflection. Then, a reviews of instructional scaffolding, its types and techniques were conducted to choose the kinds of strategies that were most suitable for the current research. Finally, other research studies related to language learning skills including reading, writing, oral fluency, and even metacognitive reading awareness which reported significant gains in terms of academic achievement were explored for new practices and tools of research. Cited in several studies, Russian researcher, Vygotsky (1896-1934) developed the socio-cultural theory of learning explaining it through the zone of proximal development (ZPD) which is referred as the potential in the child to be reflected in his cognitive development through socio-cultural interactions [19]. Vygotsky's sociocultural theory received great attention with the emergence of a more social perspective on language teaching and learning which meant that social aspects were primary for learning to take place in an individual [13]. In the context of learning a second language particularly by adults, Vygotsky's definition of ZPD was adapted to include adult learners along with children. Also, collaborative efforts with a teacher or peer in language learning determined the level of potential development against actual development [17]. Vygotsky's ZPD is explained in Figure 1 [19].

Figure 1. Zone of proximal development

Fani and Ghaemi [17] further discuss the implications of Vygotsky's ideas in teacher education by renaming the ZPD as zone of proximal teacher development (ZPTD). According to Warford [20], the two authors describe ZPTD as the difference between the potential level at which a teacher candidate might perform without assistance and the proximal level that the candidate might achieve when supported in professional practice. Elaborating more, they also emphasize improving the ZPTD through diary writing, self-scaffolding, collaborating with colleagues, conducting action research, analyzing teaching practice and having discussions with learners [17]. Referring to action research in professional practice, Stetsenko's review of Vygotsky's theory [18], the philosophy behind it and the emphasis on 'trans/formative methodology' resonates with the four-stage process of 'transformative reflection', that is, reflect-plan-apply-evaluate in effective teaching [21]. Such an engagement with transformative reflection in professional practice provides a wider context for alignment and refinement.

Reviewing concept papers on scaffolding techniques, Walqui [2] has listed six different types of instructional scaffolding to use with English learners namely: modelling, bridging, contextualization, building schema, re-presenting text, and developing metacognition. Harraqi [22] examines Walqui's conceptual framework and highlights the significance of applying it for active learning and better motivation of learners although a high level of training, time and instructional planning may be required from the instructional scaffolding. Both these references were instrumental in shortlisting the suitable scaffolding types during intervention. Besides, two levels of scaffolding are suggested by Saye and Brush [23] viz., soft, and hard. Soft refers to scaffolding by asking questions or giving constructive feedback, and hard scaffolding refers to helping with higher level thinking by giving hints or clues in solving difficult tasks. A review of some other action research articles, on English writing [11], [24]–[26], speaking [7], [9], [27], [28] or reading [8], [12], [13], [15] informed about new practices. However, most were conducted at the school level or were quasi experimental in design and implementation (pre-test post-test control group).

Morales [15] action research reports the positive effect of scaffolded intensive reading on students' reading comprehension performance in two sample English national exit exams (ENEEs) in Costa Rica. In this intervention plan, scaffolding was provided in small groups and data were collected using both quantitative and qualitative methods. By far, the layout of this study seems to be the closest to the present action research. In general, the present study attempts to determine how effectively scaffolding instruction can improve the language learning skills of Foundation year students. It is hoped that this action research will contribute to refining educational practice in improving the performance of EFL/ESL students in their English language learning. The findings and the insights gained through the cycles of change intervention answer two sub-questions: i) to what extent scaffolded instruction improved the critical reading skills of these students as EFL/ESL learners; and ii) what study skills these students have managed to improve through the experience of scaffolded instructions.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

To ensure clarity and consistency, the following operational terms apply to this research. Scaffolding instruction is breaking up the learning into chunks and providing a tool, or structure, with each chunk. Scaffolding reading, for ex: a preview or discussion on key vocabulary/small portions of the text [29]. Language learning is broadly defined as developing the ability to communicate in a second/foreign language. In the context of this action research, language learning includes language learning for critical reading and for study skills [30]. Study skills are the "techniques and strategies that help a person read or listen for specific purposes with the intent to remember" [31]. Instructional scaffolding, also known as "Vygotsky scaffolding" or just "scaffolding," is a teaching method that helps students learn more by working with a teacher or advanced students to achieve their learning goals [32].

2.1. Implementing the research plan

Students were informed about the plan of research in five initial steps. First, information sessions were conducted for voluntary participation explaining the potential mutual benefits of the activities. Second, student consent form was emailed to all, requesting them to email the filled-in forms back with their signatures. It was felt necessary to re-assure the participants that it was a learning experience to improve their language learning skills and the researcher's teaching skills. The signed forms came in time. Third, a reading prompt for the critical reading tasks under discussion was posted on the learning management system, Blackboard. Thus, students were familiarized with the reading tasks beforehand. Fourth, groups of four or five students with mixed abilities were formed on WhatsApp, each group adding the researcher for scaffolding. Finally, basic guidelines in scaffolding instructions were shared and netiquette were discussed. During the study, reading prompts with passages suitable for the students' level in English were provided as a cycle of intervention and for each cycle, there were specific tasks to perform. Students worked on those tasks in small groups and collaborated asynchronously while being supported by the course instructor.

2.2. Sampling criteria

The sample for this research were the Foundation year students enrolled in English reading and writing course during the semester, provided they: i) volunteered; ii) participated in both the cycles; and iii) completed all the surveys, language learning assessment (LLA), and checklists in all respects. At the end of both the cycles, 36 students had met all the above criteria. The present study's somewhat small sample size (N=36) is justified based on the intricacy of the model chosen by the researchers. Issues with sample size are dependent on the complexity of the model, according to Bentler and Chou [33], the suggested estimated ratio between sample size and number of parameters is 5 to 1. The ratio in this study was 18 to 1. According to previous studies [34]–[36], sample sizes comparable to those described in this study have been evaluated in a similar manner. Moreover, the insight reinforced by the process of sampling in the current study, noted in Morales [15] action research, was that a contextualized study like this should not aim to generalize any findings as applicable to a large sample though the researchers should closely examine any recurring patterns or themes that may emerge.

2.3. Design

The design of the study followed the 'apply' stage of reflective teaching through action research vis-à-vis reflect-plan-apply-evaluate [21]. A reading practice was conducted to familiarize the students with the process to be followed. The intervention through scaffolding was provided in two cycles as shown in Table 1.

During the process of scaffolding instruction, the first author, being the course-instructor, communicated with members in each group to navigate them through steps in doing an activity, prompt them when they faced any difficulty in following directions, and facilitate when they needed support with hints or clues for a higher-level task. As a reflective practitioner, it was a personal journey in teaching practice to be an active participant in ZPTD. Sample reading tasks for cycles 1 and 2 are as in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 1. Cycles of change

Cycle 1 (14 days)	Cycle 2 (14 more days)
Intervention: A passage for critical reading task	Development: Another passage for critical reading
Change:	Change:
Scaffolding instruction in small groups to comment on an assigned prompt as a team.	Scaffolding instruction in small groups to comment on an assigned prompt as well as respond to one more group's comment as a team.

Table 2. Steps in completing cycle 1

	Task
Step 1	Get to know your group and create a WhatsApp group. Name the group and add the instructor.
Step 2	Divide the independent reading passage into 4 or 5 parts depending on the members in the group and read your part and the rest of the passage.
Step 3	When you read your part, then mark the most difficult words (maximum 5). Find the meaning of these words in English, choose the meaning that you think fits the best and write the word and the meaning in the group chat. Make sure you also read and understand the words that your group members have written.
Step 4	Individual group feedback and scaffolding by the instructor.
Step 5	Overall, there are 5 to 7 key points in the whole passage. Identify those points and try to relate them with your personal experience. Each member of a group should write about a different key point.
Step 6	Write your comment on one of the key points making a personal connection in only 3 to 5 sentences including the sentence for the key point. All of you will finish this task within the next two hours.
Step 7	Individual group feedback and scaffolding, if needed, by the instructor.

Table 3. Steps in completing cycle 2

	Task
Step 1	Support the key points in your reading prompt with a fact/an example/an explanation/a reason/a definition. These supporting sentences must have some relevant information from the reading passage. Each group member will write about a key point in about 3 to 5 sentences. Submit as one paragraph.
Step 2	Individual group feedback and scaffolding by the instructor.
Step 3	Go over the comments of another group assigned to you and discuss in your group.
Step 4	Write a response by answering the following questions. Each member will respond to one question each. Question#1: Does the comment cover the broad topic, and does it cover the prompt topic given to the group? How do you know? Question#2: In your opinion, is the comment well-organized? How do you know? (A group of four members will omit this question) Question#3: What makes this comment interesting to read? Give an example. Question#4: Name one thing that you learned from the comment. How will you apply it to your reading? Question#5: One suggestion that you have for the whole group about their comment on the prompt. (Please respond to the comment, and not to the prompt)
Step 5	Individual group feedback and scaffolding, as and when needed, by the instructor.

2.4. Instrumentation

Some parallels could be drawn between the current study and the experimental research by Samar and Dehqan [13] in terms of the process of implementing the scaffolding instruction for reading comprehension activity such as the age group of the ESL group, the nature of reading text, small group distribution, the scaffolding techniques, and the format of assessments. Out of all the scaffolding techniques, soft vs hard (support provided only till needed) [23]; chunking (breaking down the information) [37]; modelling (giving clear examples), bridging (using prior knowledge) and contextualizing (making connections) [2] were used most of the times. For tools, most of Vygotsky-based action research studies compared students' test scores before and after the intervention [25], [26], [28]. Morales [15] collected data for the reading comprehension action research through triangulation, that is, from samples of English exam, field notes and research artefacts. This action research also uses triangulation with information collected from 2 surveys, 2 test scores and a checklist.

2.4.1. Student survey

With the purpose of measuring students' perception of learning after every cycle, a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire was developed from the intended learning outcomes of the reading and writing course. This questionnaire was filled out by the participants at the end of each cycle and statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS version 26. Preliminary analysis was performed to inspect the quality of the data. Univariate normality (Skewness and Kurtosis) was performed and descriptive statistics for each construct was completed. To establish the construct validity of the questionnaire, exploratory factor analysis was performed with principal axis factoring and oblimin rotation. The reliability of the items was examined by Cronbach's alpha coefficient.

2.4.2. Language learning assessment

After the tasks on a reading prompt were completed, students were asked to submit a final draft of their responses specifying their individual attempt in the group. This process was repeated after they completed each change intervention. For maintaining their language learning, students' individual achievement scores on their response to the reading prompt were computed after every cycle using a rubric which was adapted for online independent reading tasks and designed with a focus on learning English for academic purposes (EAP). The criteria on the rubric included: timely submission, clarity and organization, connection and critical thinking, spelling, length, and mechanics.

2.4.3. An observation checklist of criteria

To observe students' improvement in study skills through self-evaluation, a 4-point Likert scale checklist with eight subskills was adapted from a study skill for online reading survey proposed by Rhodes *et al.* [38] in a publication of The College Reading Association. The subskills listed in the checklist were: following directions, locating information, selecting information, organizing information, retaining information, interpreting the graphic information, reading flexibility and good study habits. Students were asked to reflect on their experience related to the eight subskills mentioned in the checklist and complete this checklist.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Student survey

The mean, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis for the constructs, as presented in Table 4 were used to check the normality assumption. All mean scores were above the midpoint of 3.00, indicating an overall positive response to the progress being made in achieving the required learning outcomes. The standard deviation range indicated that participants' responses were dispersed close to the mean. Absolute skewness and kurtosis values are less than 3 and less than 10, respectively, confirming that the data met the assumption of the multivariate normal distribution of the data [39].

The internal consistency of the items on the questionnaire was assessed using the Cronbach's alpha coefficient which for both student surveys (SS1 and SS2) was exceeding 0.70, which is generally used as the threshold for an acceptable reliability coefficient [40]. This confirms the reliability or internal consistency of the scales (SS1 and SS2). In factor analysis, as shown in Table 5, the items of the two scales were subjected to principal axis factoring and oblimin rotation, using SPSS version 27. Factor loadings of the items were greater than the cut off of 0.4, as recommended by Matsunaga [41].

Reflecting further on mean scores in Table 4, responses being prompt and positive could be due to the improvement in skills that was obvious to students themselves in terms of the learning outcomes. Significantly improved ratings in SS2 were on Q1, Q7, and Q8 showing many students' gains from the two

cycles. These items are: I can support my ideas with relevant examples or other forms of evidence (Q7); I can relate with a text and connect it with my personal experience (Q8), and I can skim texts for main ideas (Q1).

These specific items directly relate to some of the scaffolding strategies that were used, namely: modelling (giving clear examples), bridging (using prior knowledge), and contextualizing (making connections) [2]. This was evidence of students' perception of learning from scaffolding. In a nutshell, instructional activities and scaffolding strategies aligned well with learning outcomes of the course because students could see the benefits of those tasks.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics for SS1 and SS2 scales

Construct	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	Cronbach alpha
SS2	Q1	4.61	0.55	-1.02	0.06	0.84
	Q2	4.53	0.61	-0.92	-0.08	
	Q3	4.42	0.69	-0.78	-0.51	
	Q4	4.17	0.78	-1.09	1.77	
	Q5	4.87	0.63	-1.75	1.95	
	Q6	4.39	0.73	-0.77	-0.68	
	Q7	4.64	0.64	-1.60	1.45	
	Q8	4.64	0.54	-1.16	0.42	
	Q9	4.50	0.81	-1.53	1.54	
SS1	Q1	3.89	0.75	-0.25	-0.12	0.89
	Q2	3.94	0.75	0.09	-1.18	
	Q3	3.72	0.85	-0.31	-0.32	
	Q4	3.61	0.96	-0.54	0.29	
	Q5	4.19	0.89	-1.70	4.19	
	Q6	3.72	1.03	-1.05	1.17	
	Q7	3.69	0.75	0.15	-0.46	
	Q8	3.97	0.70	-0.50	0.81	
	Q9	3.78	1.05	-0.64	-0.01	

Table 5. Factor loadings for individual items

Item	Factor loading	
	SS1	SS2
Q1	0.70	
Q2	0.74	
Q3	0.67	
Q4	0.71	
Q5	0.69	
Q6	0.83	
Q7	0.61	
Q8	0.62	
Q9	0.69	
Q1		0.57
Q2		0.87
Q3		0.50
Q4		0.52
Q5		0.84
Q6		0.75
Q7		0.89
Q8		0.64
Q9		0.72
% variance	54.12%	44.69%

3.2. Language learning assessment

A paired-sample t-test was conducted with IBM SPSS version 26 to evaluate the impact of scaffolding instruction on the language learning achievement scores of students. There was a statistically significant increase in scores from LLA#1 to LLA#2. The mean increase was -0.92 with 95% confidence interval ranging from -1.045 to -0.80. The effect size statistic (0.37) indicated a small effect size [42]. Figure 2 shows a normal distribution in students' achievement scores after cycle 1, but after cycle 2, this difference narrowed down to only 80% to 90% range. Also supported by Samar and Dehqan [13], this could be due to the collaborative nature of the tasks.

To substantiate the above, cycles 1 and 2 scores were compared with the scores of a reading practice before the intervention. The students worked individually on a reading task and the feedback given to them revealed that they needed to read the prompt correctly and completely; comment on all parts; refer to the reading when they commented on it; make personal connections; follow the netiquette and the given format

and avoid using the translator. Then the scores ranged from 50% to 79%. Figure 3 shows the comparison. The findings align with the qualitative case study by Hashim and Yusoff [43] exploring the use of reflective practice by English language teachers which emphasized continuous learning, making connections through code-switching, and using students' prior knowledge.

Figure 2. Distribution of language learning scores after cycles 1 and 2

Figure 3. Students' language learning scores compared with practice before intervention

3.3. Study skills observation checklist

The observation checklist was students' self-evaluation of the improvement made in study skills for reading. The relationship between items on the study skills checklist was investigated using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient with IBM SPSS version 26 as shown in Table 6. The internal consistency of the items on the questionnaire was assessed using the Cronbach's alpha coefficient which was 0.91. This confirms the reliability or internal consistency of the 36-items on the checklist.

Table 6. Correlation

SN	Scale- # of items	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	Follow directions (3)	1							
2	Locate info (19)	0.71**	1						
3	Select info (2)	0.60**	0.60**	1					
4	Org info (2)	0.35*	0.38*	0.10	1				
5	Retain info (5)	0.33	0.33	0.42*	0.49**	1			
6	Graphics (1)	0.32	0.36*	0.25	0.14	0.25	1		
7	Reading flexibly (3)	0.54**	0.44**	0.47**	0.21	0.42*	0.21	1	
8	Study habits (1)	0.34*	0.39*	0.11	0.47**	0.25	-0.08	0.30	1

**p<0.01; *p<0.05

Another pattern was observed in major subskills from Table 6, as shown in Figure 4. Concurring that students rated following directions, graphics, and study habits higher since many of them had got more adapt at navigating through tasks, it was observed that ‘organizing information’ remained a forte generally for the group leaders who organized the ideas and posted them.

Figure 4. Mean scores of responses on subskills

3.4. Reflections from students

A qualitative analysis of students’ remarks and reflective feedback on the whole experience revealed that many of them admitted having benefitted from the skills they had learned as a few highlights are listed echoing different aspects of critical reading and study skills:

“I was reading in an awful way to take the idea only without going deep into the details. I see now that I must read the text more than once.” (Improving study habits).

“I improved a lot this semester. First, I can see a big difference in my reading because of the improvement in skimming and scanning skills. It helped me a lot to find the information in a short time.” (Locating information).

“I really enjoy this reading and I learned how to reply for others’ comments.” (Critical reading).

“It was a nice experience. I really appreciated the feedbacks and suggestions.” (Scaffolding techniques).

“Thank you for helping us getting and understanding the purpose of each task.” (Following directions).

“I learned a lot. I developed my reading skills, and I enjoyed working with the members of my group, they were helpful and friendly.” (Reading skills in a small group).

“I see a slight improvement in my reading skills, and I learned a lot from my group members like how I correct my grammar mistakes and how we can organize our ideas. I hope we can work together again.” (Learning from groups).

Reinforcing the students’ reflections and engagement with professional practice, the three emerging themes point to the following: i) operating scaffolding instruction in small groups was constructive, convenient, and efficient as Race [44] also supports small-group contexts for ‘deep learning’; ii) asynchronous online discussions on independent reading tasks which were pre-planned and well-structured with clear scaffolding instructions contributed to better student participation. A university level study [45] refers to asynchronous online discussions on a reading task and small group setting as significant factors in student success. In addition, a study conducted in a Saudi Arabian university [28] emphasizes, the success in using and benefiting from instructional strategies depends on the amount of effort and skills that the teacher has rather than his pedagogical content knowledge; and iii) in practicing scaffolding, especially in mixed-ability small groups, ‘as and when needed’ [23] is an important mantra for success.

3.5. Limitations and the future plan of action

Besides many strengths, this study had two major limitations: i) like the other two tools, observation checklists should be filled out after each cycle to measure ‘improvement’ in study skills; and ii) due to time constraints, peer learning and evaluation did not get sufficient attention and should have been integrated with

the checklist evaluations. It should be part of the change in one of the cycles to examine its effect on students' perception and learning achievement. Overall, the insights gained will be more sustainable in improving reading comprehension if the action research is reinforced with more focused attention to peer learning and for a longer duration. Hence as part of future vision, the recommendations are: for critical reading practice, more variety of reading tasks and reading strategies should be applied while continuing with the ones already applied. For example, scaffolding instruction should be practiced with diverse levels of students using metacognitive reading awareness. Besides, more peer learning may be attained by extending the timeline to two more weeks and the cycles of intervention to three instead of two. More peer evaluation and better self-awareness will enable the students to also focus on a specific set of study skills in reading. For example: organizing, retaining, and locating information. Relating metacognitive reading awareness to finding out the meaning of information is also supported by mixed-methods exploratory studies [46], [47], a review article [22], a small case study [11], and an online collaborative multimethod study [48].

4. CONCLUSION

Findings from this action research align with previous conclusions of the effectiveness of scaffolding instruction. The critical reading skills and the study skills of the Foundation year EFL/ESL students were found to have improved. The proposed practice represented in scaffolding instruction with these students to support their English language learning as EFL/ESL learners yielded positive feedback and measurable improvement in results. Students were also found to have developed stronger and more independent study skills. All the three tools reliably and consistently demonstrated notable success in improving the language learning skills of the target group of students. The qualitative feedback from the students emphasized the importance of working with small groups, a well-organized instructional plan and scaffolding only till needed.

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